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**AYRIM GETEROATOMLI ALDEGIDLARNI ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF
KATALITIK SISTEMASIDA ALKINLASH JARAYONI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ishida ilk bor ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF katalitik sistema yordamida atsetilen, fenilatsetilen bilan ayrim aldegidlar– tiofen-2-karbaldegid, 3-metiltiofen-2-karbaldegid, furan-2-karbaldegid, piridin-3-karbaldegid, xinolin-2-karbaldegid va 3-brom-4-piridinkarbaldegidlar bilan enantiosektiv etinillash reaksiyalari asosida mos ravishdagi atsetilen spirtlarini sintez qilish reaksiyalari o'rganilgan. Qo'llanilgan kompleks sistemaning atsetilen spirtlarini hosil bo'lish samaradorligiga ta'siri taklif etilgan va reaksiya mexanizmlari keltirilgan. Mahsulot unumiga ta'sir qiluvchi bir qator omillar – harorat, reaksiya davomiyligi, katalizator va erituvchilar, substrat va reagentlar miqdori ta'siri tadqiq qilingan. Olingan natijalar asosida jarayonlar uchun eng muqobil sharoitlar topilgan. Sintez qilingan atsetilen spirtlarining tarkibi, tozaligi, tuzilishi va kvant-kimyoviy xossalari zamonaviy fizik-kimyoviy usullarda isbotlangan. Sintez qilingan atsetilen spirtlari unumining samaradorlik qatorlari aniqlangan.

Tayanch so'zlar: aldegidlar, atsetilen, fenilatsetilen, ProPhenol, tetragidrofuran, dimetilruks, alkinillash, atsetilen spirtlari, reaksiya mexanizmi, mahsulot unumi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании впервые использована каталитическая система ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/ТГФ, ацетилен, фенилацетилен и некоторые альдегиды - тиофен-2-карбальдегид, 3-метилтиофен-2-карбальдегид, фуран-2-карбальдегид, пиридин-3-карбальдегид, хинолин-2-карбальдегидом и 3-бром-4-пиридинкарбальдегидом на основе реакций энантиоселективного этинирования изучены реакции синтеза соответствующих ацетиленовых спиртов. Предложено влияние используемой системы на эффективность образования ацетиленовых спиртов и представлены механизмы реакции.

Изучен ряд факторов, влияющих на выход продукта, - температура, продолжительность реакции, влияние количества катализатора и растворителей, субстрата и реагентов. На основе полученных результатов были найдены наиболее альтернативные условия протекания процессов. Состав, чистота, строение и квантово-химические свойства доказаны современными физико-химическими методами синтезированных ацетиленовых спиртов.

Ключевые слова: альдегиды, ацетилен, фенилацетилен, профенол, тетрагидрофуран, диметилцинк, алкинирование, ацетиленовые спирты, механизм реакции, выход продукта.

Abstract: In this research work, for the first time, using ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF catalytic system, acetylene, phenylacetylene and some aldehydes – thiophene-2-carbaldehyde, 3-methylthiophene-2-carbaldehyde, furan-2-carbaldehyde, pyridine-3-carbaldehyde, quinoline-2-carbaldehyde and 3-bromo-4-pyridinecarbaldehyde, based on enantioselective ethynylation reactions with reactions for the synthesis of corresponding acetylene alcohols were studied. The effect of the used complex systems on the efficiency of the formation of acetylene alcohols is proposed and the reaction mechanisms are presented. A number of factors affecting product yield - temperature, duration of reaction, influence of amount of catalyst and solvents, substrate and reagents - were studied. Based on the obtained results, the most alternative conditions for the processes were found. The composition, purity, structure and quantum-chemical properties of the synthesized acetylene alcohols have been proven by modern physico-chemical methods. The efficiency ranges for the production of synthesized acetylene alcohols have been determined.

Keywords: aldehydes, acetylene, phenylacetylene, ProPhenol, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylzinc, alkynylation, acetylene alcohols, reaction mechanism, product yield.

Molekulasi tarkibida geteroatom o‘rinbosarlar saqlagan atsetilen spirtlari o‘zining biologik hususiyatlari yuqoriligi bilan, tibbiyot sohasida qator dori vositalar ishlab chiqarishda, qishloq ho‘jaligi va kimyo sanoatida yangi turdagi organik moddalar sintez qilishda aсосiy qurilish bloki sifatida keng qo‘llanilib kelmoqda [1-3]. Atsetilen spirtlarini sintez qilishda molekulasida geteroatom o‘rinbosarlar saqlagan aldegidlardan foydalanish, ularning biologik faolligini oshirishga yordam beradi [4]. Shuningdek, 40 °C haroratda InBr₃/BINOL kompleks katalitik sistema yordamida aldegidlarning yuqori enantioselektiv alkinillash natijasida atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilingan [5]. Yumshoq sharoitda Cu(O‘Bu) va TRAP katalizatori ishtirokida aromatik aldegidlarga terminal alkinlarni enantioselektiv qo‘shilishi natijasida 56% unum bilan atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilingan [6]. Benzaldegidni 24 soat davomida, 0 °C haroratda assimetrik alkinillanish reaksiyasi uchun katalizator Ti(OⁱPr)₄/Et₂Zn

va ligand 1-(4-fenilxinazolin-2-il)etanoldan foydalanib amalga oshirilgan [7]. Harorat 123 °C da trimetilatsetilenni n-BuLi ishtirokida benzaldegid bilan reaksiyasi natijasida 98% unum bilan atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilingan Ushbu usul bilan substrat benzaldegid va bir qator sililatsetilenlar (TES, TBS, Ph₃Si, Ph₂MeSi) reaksiyalari ham olib borilgan [8]. Xitoy olimlari tomonidan C1 birligi sifatida ommaviy sanoat mahsuloti rongalitini qo‘llash orqali terminal alkinlardan birlamchi propargil spirtlarini sintez qilish metodi ishlab chiqildi. Bunda 100 °C haroratdan ‘BuOK/DMSO-*d6* katalitik sistemadan foydalanilgan va yuqori unum bilan birlamchi propargil spirtlari sintez qilingan [9]. Bu₄NOH/H₂O/DMSO katalitik komponentidan foydalanib, aromatik va alifatik aldegidlarni fenilatsetilen bilan reaksiyasi amalga oshirilgan, natijada 91% unum bilan aromatik atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilingan [10]. Izlanishlar natijasida yumshoq sharoitda CuI/Et₃N/KOH/DMSO katalitik sistema ishtirokida terminal alkin va paraformaldegididan birlamchi propargil spirtlari sintez qilingan [11]. Fenilatsetilen va geksin-1 ishtirokida aromatik, alifatik va vinil aldegidlarni xona haroratida alkinlash jarayoni natijasida, 98% unum bilan 1-(3-xlorfenil)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, 1-(2,4-xlorfenil)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1 kabi propargil spirtlari sintezi amalga oshirilgan [12]. Korea olimlari tomonidan 120 °C haroratda ZnO katalizatori ishtirokida aldegidlarga terminal alkinlarni to‘g‘ridan to‘g‘ri birikish reaksiyalari ishlab chiqilgan va yuqori unum bilan atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilingan [13]. Monoalmashingan atsetilen birikmasiga ruxetilat va tetragidrofuran ishtirokida aldegidlarni ta‘sir ettirib ikkilamchi atsetilen spirtlari olingan. Reaksiya 0 °C haroratda olib borilgan va atsetilen spirtlari 81-98% unum bilan sintez qilingan [14]. Barry M. Trost va Jing Wang va uning jamoadoshlari aldegidlarning enantioselektiv alkinillanishini yangi usulini ishlab chiqdilar. Jarayon 4 °C haroratda toluol eritmasida, metil propiolatni Zn-ProPhenol katalizatori ishtirokida olib borilgan. [15-16]. Ti(OiPr)₄ va Zn(OTf)₂ katalizatorlaridan foydalanmasdan aldegidlarga fenilatsetilenning assimetrik qo‘shilishini efedrin hosilasi sulfamid amin spiriti asosida olib bordilar va 99% unumdorlik bilan propargil spirtlarini sintez qilishga erishdilar. Bunga sabab ligandning sulfamid - amin qismi alkinlanish paytida reaksiyani yanada tezlashishiga imkon yaratganini aniqladilar [17-18]. Monoalmashingan atsetilen birikmasiga ruxetilat va tetragidrofuran ishtirokida aldegidlarni ta‘sir ettirib ikkilamchi atsetilen spirtlari olingan. Reaksiya 0 °C haroratda olib borilgan va atsetilen spirtlari 81-98% unum bilan sintez qilingan [19].

Tajriba qismi *ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF katalitik sistema ishtirokida atsetilen spirtlari sintezi.* (Na‘muna sifatida 1-(furanil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1 sintezi

keltirilgan.) Reaksiya yuqori haroratga bardoshli shaffof shishali hajmi 2000 ml bo'lgan to'rt og'izli kolbaga qaytarma sovutkich, tomizgich voronka, termometr, aralastirgich o'rnatilgan sistemada amalga oshiriladi. Kolbaga dastlab 120 ml tetragidrofuran solinib, unga 95 g (1 mol) dimetilruks, 127,7 g (1,25 mol) fenilatsetilen argon atmosferasida ohistalik bilan qo'shildi va 60 minut davomida muntazam aralastirib turiladi. Shundan so'ng aralashmaga 60 minut davomida 159,7g ProPhenol ligandining 120 ml tetragidrofuran eritmasi va 96 g (1 mol) furan-2-karbaldegid ohistalik bilan tomizildi. Reaksiya germetik holatda -5 0 °C haroratgacha sovutiladi va 22 soat mobaynida aralastiriladi, shundan so'ng aralashma NH₄Cl (50 ml) ning to'yingan suvli eritmasi bilan to'yintirildi va aralastirildi. Organik qism ajratish uchun dietilefir (3×100 ml) yordamida ekstraksiyalanib, suv (3×50 ml) bilan yuviladi. Organik qatlam Na₂SO₄ yordamida quritiladi va erituvchilar oddiy sharoitda haydab olinadi. Organik qatlam tarkibidan mahsulotni tozalab olish uchun silikagel 60 kolonkali xromatografiyada elyuyentlardan (CH₂Cl₂:Et₂O 20:1) o'tkaziladi. Natijada 87% unum bilan 1-(furanil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1 sintez qilindi. Shuningdek sistemada 7% qo'shimcha mahsulot va 6% reaksiyaga kirishmagan furan-2-karbaldegid borligi aniqlandi. Ushbu usul bilan **9** - 1-(tiofenil-2)propin-2-ol-1, **10** - 1-(3-metiltiofenil-2)propin-2-ol-1, **11** - 1-(furanil-2)propin-2-ol-1, **12** - 1-(piridinil-3)propin-2-ol-1, **13** - 1-(xinolinil-2)propin-2-ol-1, **14** - 1-(3-brompiridinil-4)propin-2-ol-1, **15** - 1-(tiofenil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, **16** - 1-(3-metiltiofenil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, **17** - 1-(furanil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, **18** - 1-(piridinil-3)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, **19** - 1-(xinolinil-2)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1, **20** - 1-(3-brompiridinil-4)-3-fenilpropin-2-ol-1 atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilindi.

Natijalar va munozaralar. ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF katalitik sistema ishtirokida ayrim geteroatomli aldegidlar- tiofen-2-karbaldegid, 3-metiltiofen-2-karbaldegid, furan-2-karbaldegid, piridin-3-karbaldegid, xinolin-2-karbaldegid va 3-brom-4-piridinkarbaldegidni atsetilen, fenilatsetilen alkinillash reaksiyasi asosida yangi turdagi atsetilen spirtlari sintezi o'rganilgan. Reaksiya sxemasi adabiyot manbaalari asosida quyidagicha taklif etildi [20].

Tanlangan ayrim aldegidlar– tiofen-2-karbaldegid, 3-metiltiofen-2-karbaldegid, furan-2-karbaldegid, piridin-3-karbaldegid, xinolin-2-karbaldegid va 3-brom-4-piridinkarbaldegidlarni alkinlar- atsetilen, fenilatsetilen, ishtirokida alkinillash jarayoni uchun taklif etilgan katalitik sistema ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF ning boshlang‘ich moddalar massasiga nisbatan olingan mol miqdori ta’siri tahlil qilindi (1-Jadval). Boshlang‘ich moddalar va katalitik sistema mol miqdorlari 1:1,25:0,25:1 mol nisbatlarda, erituvchi tetragidrofuran, -5-0 °C haroratda, 24 soat davomida olib borilganda, sistemada molekula va ionlar to‘qnashuvlar soni ortishi asosida geteroatom atsetilen spirtlarining unumdorligi yuqori bo‘lishi kuzatildi. Aksincha reaksiya jarayonida boshlang‘ich moddalar miqdoriga nisbatan ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF mol miqdorlari teng nisbatda olinmaganligi sistemada reaksiyon markazlarning yetarli darajada hosil bo‘lmasligi hisobiga mahsulot unumiing selektivligi pasayishiga sabab bo‘ldi.

1-Jadval

**Atsetilen spirtlari unumiga boshlang‘ich moddalar va katalitik sistema mol miqdorlari nisbatlari ta’siri
 (reaksiya davomiyligi 24 soat, reaksiya harorati -5- 0 °C)**

Atsetilen spirtlari	Atsetilen spirtlari unumi, %			
	Aldegid:Alkin:ProPhenol:Me ₂ Zn			
	0,5:1:0,5:1	1:1:1:1	1:1,25:0,25:1	1:0,5:1:1
9	60	55	70	65
10	64	60	73	68
11	80	76	89	85
12	72	69	81	76
13	69	64	77	73
14	80	75	88	84
15	55	50	64	60
16	57	53	67	62
17	78	74	87	83
18	65	62	75	70
19	63	58	72	67

20	70	65	80	75
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Alkin miqdorining katalitik sistemaga nisbatan ortiqcha olinganligi sistemadagi suv bilan reaksiyaga kirishib, gidrolizlanishi natijasida qo‘shimcha moddalarning hosil bo‘lishiga imkon yaratdi va unumning pasayishiga sabab bo‘ldi. Reaksiya jarayoni davomida unumdorlikni oshirish maqsadida ketonlarning miqdori oshirilganda, reaksiya unumining pasayishi va ketonlarning to‘liq alkinillanishi uchun alkin miqdori yetishmaganligi, aldol yon mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarilishi kuzatildi.

Atsetilen spirtlarini sintez qilish jarayonida mahsulot unumiga harorat ta’siri ham o‘rganildi. Reaksiya $-15 \div 10$ °C harorat oralig‘ida olib borildi (1-Rasm).

1-Rasm. Atsetilen spirtlari unumiga harorat ta’siri (boshlang‘ich moddalar va katalitik sistema mol miqdorlari 1:1,25:0,25:1 mol nisbatlarda, erituvchi tetragidrofuran, reaksiya davomiyligi 24 soat)

Reaksiya -15 °C haroratda olib borilganda katalizatorning eruvchanligi va faolligi juda past namoyon qilganligi kuzatildi. Jarayonning haroratini $-5-0$ °C gacha oshirilganda mahsulot unumining yuqori bo‘lganligi aniqlandi. Jarayonning harorati 10 °C ga ko‘tarilganda sistemada reaksiyaning faollanish energiyasi ortishi hisobiga qaytar jarayonning ro‘y berishi orqali asosiy mahsulot unumining pasayishiga sabab bo‘ldi.

Sintez qilingan atsetilen spirtlarining tozaligi, tarkibi va tuzilishi IQ-, ^1H -YaMR, ^{13}C -YaMR spektroskopiya, xromatografiya kabi zamonaviy fizik-imyoviy tadqiqot usullari yordamida isbotlandi, atomlarining xossalari HyperChem Activation 8 paketi STAT dasturi asosida hossalari va passonline dasturi orqali biologik hossalari o‘rganildi.

XULOSALAR

Ilk marta ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF katalitik sistemasi yordamida malekulasi tarkibida geteroatom saqlagan aldegidlarni alkinlar bilan etinillash reaksiyasi asosida atsetilen spirtlari sintez qilish jarayoni tadqiq qilindi.

Olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra ProPhenol/Me₂Zn/TGF katalitik sistemasida alkinlar- atsetilen, fenilatsetilenning ayrim aldegidlar- tiofen-2-karbaldegid, 3-metiltiofen-2-karbaldegid, furan-2-karbaldegid, piridin-3-karbaldegid, xinolin-2-karbaldegid va 3-brom-4-piridinkarbaldegidlar bilan reaksiya uchun eng muqobil sharoiti topildi, unga ko'ra boshlang'ich moddalar va katalitik sistema miqdori 1:1,25:0,25:1 mol nisbatda, harorat -5- 0 °C, erituvchi tetragidrofuran, reaksiya davomiyligi 24 soat bo'lganda 1-70%, 2-73%, 3-89%, 4-81%. 5-77%, 6-88%, 7-64%, 8-67%, 9-87%, 10-75%, 11-72%, 12-80% atsetilen spirtlari eng yuqori unum bilan sintez qilindi.

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